

Example Data Management Plan – complete version with full responses

Prediction of di-nucleotide-specific DNA-binding sites in proteins using neural networks

Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW) Example Data Management Plan

Complete version with full responses

Organisation
ELIXIR-UK

Created by

Munazah
Andrabi

[0000-0002-7718-5109](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7718-5109)

Based on

Based on Standard DMP template for Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council (BBSRC) 2024

Funded by the [ELIXIR-UK: FAIR Data Stewardship training UKRI award \(MR/V038966/1\)](#) and [BioFAIR](#)

(Q1) Proposal name

Prediction of di-nucleotide-specific DNA-binding sites in proteins using neural networks.

(Q2) Description of the data: Type of study

This is a computational study using 3D crystal structures of protein-DNA (PDNA) complexes from the Protein Data Bank (PDB) ([rscb.org](https://www.rcsb.org)).

(Q3) Description of the data: Types of data

Quantitative data will be generated from PDB structures (input data) and Neural Network models trained on the input data. Raw data will be saved as csv and text files. Analysed data will be presented in the forms of graphs saved as images.

(Q4) Description of the data: Origin of the data

Existing 3D crystal structures of PDNA complexes from the PDB will be the main source of input data for our analysis. New data will be generated during the study while doing the statistical analysis and prediction of the DNA binding sites on proteins using Neural Networks.

(Q5) Description of the data: Format and scale of the data

All input data downloaded from the PDB will be in the pdb format which is essentially a text format. This data will be analysed and prepared to train the neural network models eventually leading to the prediction results. Raw data will be saved as csv and text files. Analysed data will be presented in the forms of graphs and images.

For the analysis and data preparation Jupyter notebooks in combination with R programming will be used. For Neural Network training and prediction we intend to use the SNNS software.

We expect a data volume of around 1 terabyte to be generated during the analysis.

(Q6) Managing, storing and curating data

Raw, intermediate and analysed data will all be stored and curated on the Computational infrastructure available in the research

lab. The lab has a well established computational cluster for internal use which implements a dual-factor authentication system and regular backup.

Metadata will be recorded for each raw and processed data in accompanying README files.

(Q7) Metadata standards and data documentation

We will comply with the DOME-ML and Open Neural Network Exchange (ONNX) community-wide guidelines, recommendations and checklists for machine learning models.

Comprehensive documentation will be provided about:

- Model's requirements, design, usage, and output formats.
- Version control will be implemented from models
- Model's training data, architecture, hyperparameters, and performance

Analysis pipelines will be made available on GitHub with README files.

(Q8) Data preservation strategy and standards

During the span of the project, raw, intermediate and analysed data will be stored and curated on the computational infrastructure available in the research lab.

After publication all input datasets will be made publicly available on OpenML. Machine Learning models will be shared on public platforms (e.g. GitHub or HuggingFace) to improve accessibility. The models will be made available according to the MIT License. Statistical analysis and other results will be provided as supplementary data with the publication.

(Q9) Where will data be shared?

After publication all input datasets will be made publicly available on OpenML. Machine Learning models will be shared on public platforms (e.g. GitHub or HuggingFace) to improve accessibility. The models will be made available according to the MIT License.

Statistical analysis and other results will be provided as supplementary data with the publication. Analysis pipelines will be made available on Zenodo.

(Q10) When will data be available?

Data will be made publicly available immediately after the publication.

(Q11) How will data be made findable and accessible?

After publication all input datasets will be made publicly available on OpenML. Machine Learning models will be shared on public platforms (e.g. GitHub or HuggingFace) to improve accessibility. The models will be assigned a unique and persistent identifier and linked to the model's metadata. Models will be made available according to the MIT License.

Statistical analysis and other results will be provided as supplementary data with the publication. Analysis pipelines will be made available on Zenodo.

(Q12) How will data be made reusable?

Appropriate metadata following the DOME-ML and Open Neural Network Exchange (ONNX) recommendations will be provided with the ML models. Input data will be shared with metadata on OpenML.

Detailed methodology about data preparation and analysis will also be provided in the methodology and supplementary methodology of the publication.

(Q13) Restrictions or delays to sharing, with planned actions to limit such restrictions

We do not envisage any restrictions or delays in making the data available. No restrictions will be placed on the data.

(Q14) Secondary use

Data and ML models will be immediately available for secondary reuse by researchers after the publication.

(Q15) Formal information/data security standards

Not applicable

(Q16) Main risks to data security

There are no issues of risk or confidentiality associated with this study since the source data used in this computational analysis is either publicly available or generated synthetically.

(Q17) Capabilities

Raw, intermediate and analysed data will all be stored and curated on the Computational infrastructure available in the research lab. The lab has a well established computational cluster for internal use which

implements dual-factor authentication system and regular backup.

There is no specific support for data management and all responsibilities will be looked after by the researchers themselves.

(Q18) Maintaining and implementing the Data Management Plan

DMP will be a standing item on project meeting agenda and the DMP will be revised as and when required during the execution of the project. Data Stewardship Wizard will be used to ensure and enable track changes and FAIRification of data and metadata.

(Q19) Environmental considerations

The University is committed to zero direct carbon emissions by 2038 and has taken various measures to achieve that. It uses the Laboratory Efficiency Assessment Framework (LEAF) guidance framework to improve the sustainability and efficiency of research and laboratory spaces.